

Real Wave Quantum Mechanics: Solutions for 2-D Simple Harmonic Potential Well

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Abstract

In [Ewins(2021)] it was shown that a theory based on real waves (Self Interacting Wave Fields: SIWF) could underlie the Schrödinger equation and replicate the Probability Density Functions (PDFs) for 1-D potentials with mass density distributions. The present paper describes extension of the calculations to a 2-D Simple Harmonic Oscillator (SHO) potential, using the same matrix eigenvalue method. A matrix, F_R , is generated to encapsulate the geometric and phase relationships between FRs on a grid. F_R is complex and symmetric but not Hermitian. When the SHO potential and a vacuum energy term, V_v , are incorporated, the eigenvectors of F_R are clearly similar to those produced by the Schrödinger equation (including the degeneracy structure) but additionally show an internal phase structure not associated with Schrödinger PDFs. The complex eigenvalues can be normalized by precise tuning of V_v . Repeated application of F_R to an eigenfunction results in a phase drift in the same direction that the FRs rotate. A mechanism is presented which shows how this leads to the discrete energy levels which typify QM. It is concluded that Schrödinger's equation is an approximation to the Real Wave (SIWF) theory.

1 Introduction

The paper [Ewins(2021)] introduced the main concepts of Self Interacting Wave Field (SIWF) theory and showed that it gives results consistent with those of Quantum Mechanics (QM) for 1-dimensional systems such as the square well and simple harmonic oscillator (SHO) potentials. Unfortunately, a 1-dimensional system suppresses many of the interesting features of SIWF, which is based on the rotation of Field Rotators (FRs) and their interaction via physical reaction waves propagating in at least two dimensions. In this paper, small 2-D SHO potential systems are examined using an extended matrix method.

2 Method

2.1 Differences between 1-D and 2-D

In 2-dimensions we must consider a grid of FRs each interacting with all the others. Note that choosing a grid formation is not the same as using some arbitrary grid for finite difference purposes, because we are specifying that an FR will exist at each of these points. Of course, nature might have other ideas about the placement of the FRs, but this would require something other than a matrix style of solution. Choosing a matrix for a simple 2-D model might be valid and certainly leads to enlightening results, but for 3-D systems such as the hydrogen atom it is not expected to be viable.

The new feature introduced in the move from 1-D to 2-D is that contributions from FRs not on the same physical rows or columns must be considered. In general these will not be exhibiting Phase Direction Correlation (PDC). For example, in a unit square of FRs, those on opposite corners are separated by $1/\sqrt{2}$ wavelengths: they cannot be in PDC, but their mutual contributions must still be taken into account.

2.2 Building the F_R Matrix

We wish to use the matrix method to find the eigenvalues and eigenvectors for a system of equations represented in the form

$$F_R\psi = \lambda\psi \quad (1)$$

where F_R is the required matrix and ψ is a column vector with one entry for each FR containing a complex number which encodes its phase and amplitude. We seek the eigenvector ψ^n s for which the action of the F_R matrix does no more than multiply ψ^n values by some complex number, λ_n , which is the eigenvalue corresponding to the n th eigenvector.

Consider the simplest case of a 2 by 2 array of FR locations

$$\begin{bmatrix} \psi_{0,0} & \psi_{0,1} \\ \psi_{1,0} & \psi_{1,1} \end{bmatrix}$$

The interactions between them can be represented in matrix form as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_{0,0} & \beta_{\Delta i, \Delta j} & \beta_{\Delta i, \Delta j} & \beta_{\Delta i, \Delta j} \\ \beta_{\Delta i, \Delta j} & V_{0,1} & \beta_{\Delta i, \Delta j} & \beta_{\Delta i, \Delta j} \\ \beta_{\Delta i, \Delta j} & \beta_{\Delta i, \Delta j} & V_{1,0} & \beta_{\Delta i, \Delta j} \\ \beta_{\Delta i, \Delta j} & \beta_{\Delta i, \Delta j} & \beta_{\Delta i, \Delta j} & V_{1,1} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \psi_{0,0} \\ \psi_{0,1} \\ \psi_{1,0} \\ \psi_{1,1} \end{bmatrix} = \lambda_n \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \psi_{0,0}^n \\ \psi_{0,1}^n \\ \psi_{1,0}^n \\ \psi_{1,1}^n \end{bmatrix}$$

For example, the equation for $\psi_{0,0}$ can be read off as

$$V_{0,0}\psi_{0,0} + \beta_{\Delta i, \Delta j}\psi_{0,1} + \beta_{\Delta i, \Delta j}\psi_{1,0} + \beta_{\Delta i, \Delta j}\psi_{1,1} = \lambda_n\psi_{0,0}^n$$

Here, n indicates the n 'th eigenvalue/eigenvector pair, and the $\beta_{\Delta i, \Delta j}$'s are geometric functions of the relative locations of the two FRs. For example, consider

the 1st row 2nd column term. Its function is to compute the contribution to $FR_{0,0}$ from $FR_{0,1}$. The distance between them in this case is 1, and they lie along the same row, allowing the contribution to be calculated as explained in Section 2.3. Now consider the 1st row 4th column entry. In this case the distance between $FR_{1,1}$ and $FR_{0,0}$ is $\sqrt{2}$ and the angle between them (from source to target) is $3\pi/4$. These geometric facts are used in calculating the contribution to be stored in the relevant β at row 1, column 4. The full-size geometric matrix of β s need only be calculated once for each grid. At run time, the off-diagonal entries will be multiplied by the factor α , which recognises that it is the reaction waves which must be summed and these have notional magnitude α times the FR amplitude. The appropriate V s are also inserted along the diagonal at run time.

2.3 Calculating the Contribution

To find the contribution a source FR makes to a target FR, the wave arriving at the target is treated as a spiral wave generated by, and having the characteristics of, the source (i.e. the source phase offset, spin and amplitude multiplied by α). The magnitude and phase of the wave arriving at the target are calculated as a complex vector. However, we cannot simply vector-sum all the contributions (as we might in the Feynman 'sum over all paths' calculation). We only want to include a wave to the extent to which it contributes to Phase Direction Correlation (PDC). It turns out that, because the geometry is fixed, we can do this once and for all, and incorporate it into the β values.

First, assume that all sources have phase offset zero and amplitude 1. We would like to perform a discrimination calculation on each arriving wave, but what angle should we be discriminating against? In [Ewins(2021)], because we were only studying grids with all the sources having the same zero phase offset, we discriminated against the angle zero. For spin 1 we subtracted the arriving phase of each wave from its direction to give a vector in 'discriminator space' having this angle difference as its angle and the arriving wave amplitude as its magnitude. Vector summation of these contributions over all sources gave the final discriminator vector. We found this had angle $\approx \pi/4$ rather than zero. If we had chosen to discriminate against $\pi/4$ the discriminator vector angle would have turned out to be zero. Thus, when we discriminate against zero, the discriminator gives us the *relative* phase angle of an FR which would have been formed at the target by the waves coming from all the sources (assumed to have zero phase offsets).

How is the fact that the sources can themselves have varying phase offsets handled? The vector ψ_n , eventually to be an eigenvector, will contain a complex number for each FR which encodes its phase offset and amplitude. In the matrix calculation, this value will be multiplied by a β value which is also encoding a discriminator phase and amplitude for a source FR with phase offset zero and unit amplitude ($\times\alpha$). Multiplying two complex numbers we multiply the magnitudes (thus correctly scaling the amplitude) and add the phases (thus setting the source contribution to the required phase offset).

The matrix F_R turns out to be symmetric but not Hermitian: complex terms either side of the diagonal have the same sign for the imaginary part. (This fact is useful in building the very large matrices involved). Because of its symmetry it proves possible to render the matrix somewhat sparse by cutting off all terms more than some selected distance from the target FR. This still results in a symmetric matrix. This has been used sparingly in the work reported here - typically for an N sided array the cut-off distance has been set at N. FRs which have significant magnitudes are usually confined to central zones, which means none of the contributions to them are omitted. FRs in corner regions may lose contributions from source FRs in the opposite corners, but as these are typically at close to zero amplitude anyway, the effect should be minimal.

2.4 Formulating the Problem

The fact that the contributions are actually reaction waves is handled in the same way as for the 1-D case, modified to reflect the 2-D problem. The essence to be captured is conservation of energy (expressed through amplitudes) in the process of

- stochastic boosting of amplitude controlled by E and V
- reduction in amplitude due to destructive interference with the reaction wave produced as the vector sum of waves from all other FRs.

In a stationary state these must balance for every FR in the structure.

For the gain:

- the relationship used in the Schrödinger equation is a starting point - essentially $\psi(E - V)$ i.e. the amplitude gains are proportional to the value of ψ with a constant of proportionality controlled by $(E - V)$. An equation of the form

$$\psi' = \psi (1 + f(E, V))$$

is postulated. The absolute gain is given by:

$$\psi' - \psi = \psi (1 + f(E, V)) - \psi$$

$$\psi' - \psi = \psi f(E, V)$$

But what is the form of $f(E, V)$? In Schrödinger's equation it is simply $(E - V)$ and the solutions identify the points where $E = V$ as points of inflection between the negative curvature (sinusoidal) and the positive curvature (inverse exponential) zones. However, ψ can be non-zero at these points so for SIWF there must be gains and $(E - V)$ cannot be used. There must be an additional constant underlying potential at all points - the vacuum potential, say V_v . Without this potential, structures would simply evaporate, and its presence resolves the issue of no gain for $E = V$. The modified gain function is:

$$f(E, V(x)) = V_v + E - V(x)$$

so the absolute gain becomes:

$$\psi' - \psi = \psi (V_v + E - V(x)) \quad (2)$$

(N.b. V_v could be written as negative. It is written as positive in this expression and results subsequently show it to have negative value.)

For the losses:

- The destructive interference losses are not proportional to the value of ψ in question - they result from the sum of the reaction waves arriving from every other FR. Factors to be considered are:
 - the reaction coefficient - taken to be the dimensionless ratio of reaction wave amplitude to FR amplitude.
 - a dimensionless constant relating the amplitude at unit distance from the FR to the notional amplitude of the FR.
 - In modelling SIWF, these constants cannot be distinguished and they are grouped together as a single entity α which is now the ratio of the amplitude of the reaction wave at distance λ_s from the FR node to the amplitude of the FR itself.
 - the phase of the contributions
- The calculated contributions are actually for the *reaction wave* as discussed in [Ewins(2021)]. This is the notional wave characterizing the non-linear interaction of FRs with the wave field. The phase of the summed contributions Σ must be negated because they are π out of phase with the FRs deemed to have formed them.

Thus

$$Gains + (-\Sigma) = 0$$

i.e.

$$Gains = \Sigma$$

Taking these considerations into account, the stationary state SIWF equation becomes:

$$\psi (V_v + E - V(x)) = \Sigma_{AllFRscontributions}$$

Rearranging and shortening the right hand terms to Σ :

$$\psi (V_v - V(x)) - \Sigma = -E\psi$$

$$\psi (V(x) - V_v) + \Sigma = E\psi$$

The resulting matrix is the same as that presented in Section 2.2 multiplied by α and with the the diagonals replaced by $V_{x,y} - V_v$

3 Results

The Python program RWQM2DSHO used to generate these results is available here. Results have been constrained by computing limitations to an 80×80 grid of FRs ¹. The grid only contains half of the FRs it should because all the FRs at the half integer points with phase offset π are omitted. Their inclusion would double the size of the matrix and exceed the available computer facilities. The impact of this remains to be checked. Eigenvectors were generated for $\alpha = 1/137$ (whimsical choice) and SHO constant $2e-6$; these values ensuring that ψ magnitudes close to the grid boundaries are vanishingly small. The SHO potential well is centred on the centre of the grid.

3.1 General form

The first 21 eigenvectors are shown in Figure 1. The plots show the magnitudes of the complex vectors rather than their squares, as this preserves more detail. The rows are based on degeneracy levels which are identified and discussed in more detail below. In general terms, plots are an intriguing mixture of those usually presented as Probability Density Functions (PDFs) for this configuration and others not so presented. The following comments are based on comparison with results derived from the Schrödinger equation presented by The University of St Andrews which can be found by clicking [here](#).

- The first three are the same.
- In row three, the 'three in a row' configuration is not seen: rather, the first and third in the row seem to be hybrids of these. The middle structure in row 3 is axially symmetric and is not present in the St Andrews simulations.
- Row four exactly matches the St Andrews forms
- Row 5 column 5 matches one of the St Andrews forms. Columns 3 and 4 seem to be symmetric hybrids, while columns 1 and 2 seem similar to the linear St Andrews forms.
- Row 6 columns 1 to 4 seem to match the St Andrews ones but columns 5 and 6 do not.

3.2 Internal Structure

The general form of the Eigenvectors is very encouraging, especially considering the highly restricted grid size. To give this some perspective, in the lowest of the hydrogen energy levels the PDF extends radially with significant density out to about 5 times the Bohr radius, which is about 20 times the Compton

¹A 90×90 grid is possible but computing time is impractically long for this essentially qualitative work. A 100×100 grid runs into memory issues.

ψ Magnitude Plots for First 21 Eigenvectors

Figure 1: 80x80 grid with cut-off distance 80, $\alpha = 1/137$, SHO constant $C = 2e-6$

Figure 2: Close up of phase arrows showing alternating phases. Grid intersects are FR locations.

wavelength. For just a 2D calculation this would require an array of up to 300 FRs square. In comparison, the eigenvectors found here fit within a 50×50 FR grid. Nevertheless, these forms show clear quantization and, with some interesting differences, follow the main predictions of the Schrödinger theory. However, there is a huge difference, because these eigenvectors exhibit an internal phase structure which is not present in the Schrödinger wave solutions. Recall that for a stationary Schrödinger state $\psi^*\psi$ is unchanging with time but the 'phase' of the PDF changes uniformly with time at a rate which equates to the energy of the state. Thus, provided that the electron is at rest, the phase is uniform across the PDF at any instant of time. Now let us look more closely at the Eigenvectors which have been generated in this work. In Figure 2 a close view of the row 2 column 1 eigenvector around one of its peaks is given. The background is a contour map of the magnitude of the vector, whilst the arrows indicate the locations and phases of each FR. As in the case of the 1-Dimensional potential, the main thing to notice is that adjacent FRs are π out of phase with each other. In [Ewins(2021)] it was concluded that it was this feature which enabled stable structures to exist because divergent summation of the harmonic series is replaced with the convergent alternating harmonic series.

Figure 3 shows the same eigenvector at a larger scale, at which it becomes apparent that the phase actually varies *across* the structure. Figure 4 shows the same thing for another eigenvector. For the Schrödinger equation, the reason for the form of eigenvectors is difficult to discern - they just 'come out of the maths'. SIWF allows us to understand why these structures exist: the phase offset differences across them means that they very nearly support each other in phase - but as the next section shows, not quite!

Figure 3: Full scale showing variation of phase direction across the structure

Figure 4: Full scale showing variation of phase direction across the structure

3.3 Eigenvalues

The eigenvalues which relate to the eigenvectors shown in Figure 1 are complex. (Recall that the F_R matrix is symmetric, but not Hermitian - which would have resulted in real eigenvalues.) Further, the eigenvalues depend on the selected value of V_v used to calculate them. For the 1D SHO, this was used to clarify that the energy levels could be consistent with QM. For the 2-D case we must select V_v differently. Referring to Equation 1

$$F_R\psi = \lambda\psi$$

we have:

- the eigenvectors ψ . These are the possible arrays of complex numbers which satisfy the matrix equation. Each matrix element encodes the phase and magnitude of an FR at a particular point in space. From the absolute square of these we hope to extract a mass density function.
- corresponding to each eigenvector we have an eigenvalue which we have shown to be complex.
- The equation says that if we operate with F_R on the ψ_n th eigenvector we will do no more than multiply each FR entry within it by the same complex λ_n . To multiply complex numbers we multiply their magnitudes and add their phases.
- It follows that for a steady state the eigenvalues must have unit magnitude, whatever their phase angle is.
- As a result, *all* FR phases within the structure will have their phase shifted by the phase of the unit eigenvalue when operated on by F_R .
- But applying a consistent phase shift to a set of rotating objects (i.e. the FRs) is equivalent to altering the frequency of their rotation, Simplistically, in quantum theory that equates to changing their energy. Quite how this plays out is discussed below.

An important finding is that we can only make the eigenvalues have unit magnitude by fine tuning the value of V_v used for each different eigenvector ². Figure 5 shows the relationship between V_v and the eigenvector number. The degeneracy exhibited was used to present Figure 1 in its echelon form. Note that there is a small amount of splitting in the group of 6 (2/4). The cause is unknown: it could be a real feature or could arise because the limited 80×80 FR array impacts on these somewhat larger eigenstructures.

In Figure 6 the V_v values are averaged over each degeneracy group. The relationship is linear within this range of n values. Figure 7 shows the variation

²In practise this was done using a Scipy optimization package. Magnitudes differing from 1 by less than 1e-10 were achieved. Note that the order in which the eigenvectors are returned from the Scipy eigenvalue package can vary depending on the value of V_v used. Care must to be taken in optimizing for the same eigenvector shape rather than n value.

Figure 5: V_v vs n ; 80x80 grid with 80 cut-off; $\alpha = 1/137$, SHO constant $C = 2e-6$

of the average phase offset plotted against the degeneracy group. This is also linear, at least in this small range. Given the linear relationships between V_v and n , and ϕ and n , it follows that there is a linear relationship between V_v and ϕ . This is shown in Figure 8 in which the points are for each V_v, ϕ pair, rather than the degeneracy group averages.

The interaction of the eigenvectors with their eigenvalues can be shown by repeatedly multiplying by them. The results have been animated and are available here for the 3rd eigenstructure with spin up and here for the 13th eigenstructure with spin down. The phases of all the FRs rotate in unison, and in the same direction as the spin. (This rotation must not be confused with the actual rotation of the FRs: it is a much slower phase drift imposed upon it.) The rate of drift depends on the angle of the eigenvalue. Figure 7 makes clear that the first eigenvector (which equates to the Schrödinger eigenfunction having the lowest energy) has the fastest rate of phase drift.

4 Discussion

4.1 Interpreting the Results

What are we to make of these results? The key facts can be summarized as follows:

- The F_R matrix has ψ_n eigenvectors which are closely related qualitatively to ³ the Schrödinger results.
- F_R is not an operator like the Hamiltonian. Operators act on a mathematical wave function and give various measurable eigenvalues. F_R acts

³If not the same as - it has not been established if the differences merely represent a different basis for the degenerate forms.

Figure 6: Average V_v for Degeneracy Groups.

Figure 7: Average Phase Shift ϕ for Degeneracy Groups.

Figure 8: Phase vs V_v

on an eigenfunction of FR values and moves them forward in time, by rotating the phase offset. It has not intentionally been formulated in this way, but the systematic phase shifting illustrated by this work invite no other interpretation. It would seem that α , rather than a ratio of amplitudes between the FR and the reaction wave, should be interpreted as a ratio of energy flows per unit of time. FR states do not jerk forward in phase for each iteration; they must drift continuously with time, so time must be explicit within F_R .

- Figure 8 showed that the 1st eigenvector (top left corner) has the highest rate of phase drift and the lowest value for V_v . To clarify what this means in terms of the gain, we refer to the gain Equation 2 :

$$\psi' - \psi = \psi (V_v + E - V(x))$$

We get for example:

- for degeneracy group 1 $\psi' - \psi = \psi (E - 1.029795 - V(x))$
- for degeneracy group 2: $\psi' - \psi = \psi (E - 1.029710 - V(x))$
- for degeneracy group 3: $\psi' - \psi = \psi (E - 1.029625 - V(x))$

The gain is the lowest for the 1st group and rises progressively thereafter. Another way of looking at this is that the 1st structure can exist with a lower gain because it is self-supporting to a higher degree (the phase drift contributes more to the rotation of the FRs).

- The reason why this might lead to different energy levels for structures was briefly discussed in Section 8.1 of [Ewins(2021)] and can now be expanded upon as illustrated in Figures 9 and 10.
 - First, in Figure 9, we consider the situation of an electron in free space. The red surface represents the frequency/intensity spectrum and we surmise its existence because free electrons exist in equilibrium with the vacuum electron field no matter what their state of motion - their thermal motion necessarily implies some spectrum of frequencies.
 - The planes represent the gain requirements of the various structures. The blue plane relates to the first eigenstructure; orange and green the second and third degeneracy groups respectively.
 - Free electrons exist⁴, so it follows that the blue plane must intersect (or possibly be tangent to) the gain spectrum . The orange and green planes do not intersect the spectrum, so the structures they represent cannot exist in free space.
 - Following the principle of Minimising Internal Kinetic Energy (MIKE), the frequency of FR rotation (i.e. the Compton frequency) will be that of the leftmost intersect.
 - moving on to Figure 10, the edge of a potential well is modelled as the higher gain spectrum shown in magenta. (Considerations of the well form etc are not relevant to this argument and are ignored.) All three planes intersect this higher spectrum, so these eigenstructures will be able to exist⁵.
 - Again applying the minimization of internal kinetic energy, the FR frequency for the three structures will be at the left hand intercepts of the planes and the enhanced spectrum.
 - Thus we see that there is a connection between structure and energy (frequency):
 - * structures are self-supporting to a degree indicted by their phase drift, which is given by the angle element of their normalized eigenvalues, and fundamentally arises from their geometry.
 - * the eigenstructures having the greatest phase drift have the lowest gain requirements

⁴We do not know what the structure of a free electron is, but from symmetry considerations we might guess its form to be similar to the first eigenvector structure. For example, let us say that we made the SHO constant smaller and smaller: then the first eigenstructure would expand, but would retain its basic form up to the limit of zero SHO constant. It must have *some* structure, otherwise it would have no angular momentum.

⁵It is also clear why there must always be at least one energy level in any potential well. If the lowest plane intersects the vacuum potential spectrum then it must certainly intersect one in which the gain is higher. A similar finding arises in standard QM. See for example section 4.2 of [French and Taylor(1979)]

- * interaction between gain requirements and the gain spectrum dictates which structures are possible.
- * where structures are possible, MIKE leads to them having progressively increasing frequencies(energies).

Figure 9: The red plane represents the frequency versus intensity spectrum for free space. The blue plane represents the required gain for the first eigenstate which is the most self-supporting structure. The orange and green planes represent the gain requirements for two higher degeneracy groups.

4.2 Re-evaluating the Schrödinger Equation

After nearly 100 years it is difficult to 'de-throne' the Schrödinger equation. In non-relativistic circumstances it works so well and gives insights that would not otherwise have been available. Yet this is its only real justification. It was never derived as some expression of an underlying reality. The process amounted to:

- we need a wave equation, because of de Broglie's findings
- it had better obey energy conservation
- it must explain the energy levels (and thus the absorption/emission spectra) of atoms.

It did these things. In addition, it identified that the energy levels could be associated with structures in physical space which could (at least probabilistically) be associated with the location of the electrons. So much science and technology

Figure 10: The zone between $x = 0$ and $x = 2$ represents the spectrum for free space, while the area between $x = 2$ and $x = 4$ represents a higher gain such as might arise in a finite square well. All three gain requirement planes now intercept the spectrum and the structures that give rise to them are allowed. The frequencies they adopt will be the lowest available to minimize internal kinetic energy i.e. the intercepts on the left hand side.

flowed from this that it is not an understatement to say that it has reshaped the 20th and 21st centuries. This leads to a particular mindset which the author has had to fight against, namely: "How will all this reduce to Schrödinger's equation?" The present work has given rise to such a good qualitative picture of QM that for the author the question has changed to "How is it that Schrödinger's equation approximates RWQM so well?" The question resolves into two distinct aspects:

- as regards the motion of particles, this was resolved in [Ewins(2021)]. It was shown that factorization of the phase harmony equations gave rise to a sinusoidal phase wave whose frequency and wave vector matched those of the Schrödinger wave. (The other wave factor describes the location of FRs and thus does not arise in standard QM.)
- as regards the interaction of particles with potential fields:
 - the present work has shown that the normalized complex eigenvalues of the F_R matrix carry an eigenstate forward in time by uniformly changing its phase. Various structures do this at different rates, leading to FRs within the structure rotating at differing frequencies, and

hence having different energies. As a result, it has been possible to illustrate how quantum behaviour arises from the lower level interaction of real waves.

- In contrast, the Hamiltonian operator in Schrödinger's equation is Hermitian and has real eigenvalues which are equated directly with the energy. It works, but without giving any inkling of how or why. Is it possible that the Schrödinger equation represents a limiting form of RWQM where the Compton Frequency of FRs is extremely high and the density of FRs becomes so large that it approaches the continuum model underlying standard QM?

The author concludes that Schrödinger's equation is an approximation of Real Wave (SIWF) Quantum Mechanics: one which makes calculation far more tractable, but does so at the expense of glossing over a level of structure which we should be attributing to fundamental particles. For the moment, this conclusion is based on qualitative arguments rather than quantitative ones, because it is very difficult to process the very large and dense matrices involved for quantitative work.

References

- [Ewins(2021)] Ron Ewins. Self interacting wave fields - a physical wave basis for quantum mechanics, 2021. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5807650>.
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